

Clay Minerals in Indian Soils

M. Sarkar and B. Chatterjee

Certain criteria for identification and estimation of individual clay mineral constituents in their binary and ternary mixtures have been established^{1,2} from a consideration of (i) the features of the potentiometric titration curves—the number of inflection points, the pH at inflection, and the ratio of total acidity at inflections; (ii) the nature of the variation of the viscosity of hydrogen systems on the progressive addition of bases and also the percentage neutralisation at which these curves show minimum or maximum; (iii) the peak temperatures, the peak heights, and the shifting of peak temperatures in the differential thermal analysis curves. An attempt has been made in the present work to identify the individual clay minerals present in some Indian soils from a consideration of the criteria established for the mixtures. For this purpose, studies have been made of the X-ray diffraction patterns and differential thermal analysis curves of hydrogen clays prepared from clays isolated from eight Indian soils constituting the four major groups of Indian soils. The variations of the electrochemical and viscous properties of the hydrogen clays on the progressive addition of bases to these have also been determined. From a consideration of the criteria mentioned above, the conclusions arrived at on the mineralogical compositions of the soils used have been detailed in Table I.

TABLE I

Clays isolated from soils from.	X-ray data.	D.T.A. data.	Chem. analysis.	Electrochem. studies.	Viscosity measurement.
Bankura (laterite)	K	K	I	K	K
	I	I	K (?)	I M	M
Suri (laterite)	K	K	I	K	K
	I	I	K (?)	I M	M
Bangalore (red)	K	K	K	K	K
		I (?)		I	
Anantapur (red)	K	I	I	I	I
		K	M	M	
			K (?)	K (?)	
Pedegaon (black)	—	M	M	M (?)	M
		I	I	I	
		K (?)			
Kalimpong (alluvial)	I	I	I	I	I
	K		M (?)	M (?)	M (?)
Berhampur (alluvial)	I	I	I	I	I
	K		K (?)	M (?)	
Uluberia (alluvial)	I	I	I	I	I
	K		M (?)	M (?)	M

N.B. K, I, and M denote respectively Kaolinite, Illite, and Montmorillonite.

*Sign of interrogation (?) indicates doubtful existence.

1. Sarkar and Chatterjee, *this Journal* 1961, **38**, 725.
2. Sarkar & Chatterjee, *Ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 948.

It will be seen from Table I that conclusions on the mineralogical compositions of soil clays, drawn on the basis of measurement of any single property, may often lead to erroneous results and individual clay mineral component in the soils can be detected only by a combination of several methods.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY AND METALLURGY,
BENGAL ENGINEERING COLLEGE, HOWRAH.

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